

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D3.4

Populated minimal metadata model for project cohorts

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1. Executive Summary

To support human cohort genomic and other “omic” data discovery and analysis across jurisdictions, basic data such as cohort participant age, sex, etc needs to be harmonised. Developing a key “minimal metadata model” of these basic attributes which should be recorded with all cohorts is critical to aid initial querying across jurisdictions for suitable dataset discovery. We review here the creation of a minimal metadata model, and provide populated example datasets, noting the model’s utility and impact and linking to additional ontologies and other tools developed to aid these efforts.

A first version of the metadata model was built based on a review of Maelstrom research data standards and a manual survey of cohort data dictionaries, which identified and incorporated overlapping core variables across CINECA cohorts. The model was then converted to Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology (GECKO) format and further expanded with additional terms. The minimal metadata model is being made broadly available to aid any project or projects, including those outside of CINECA interested in facilitating cross-jurisdictional data discovery and analysis.

Initially this was used for the CHILDb Cohort, but challenges with data sharing for real data led us to go beyond the initial objectives and construct synthetic datasets of this cohort, and then other cohorts, that are based on the minimal metadata model and real cohort data. Such datasets enable downstream application development with less concerns about data identifiability and privacy associated with real data. These synthetic data resources have proved to be extremely useful, and after one synthetic dataset was created for CHILDb in Canada, three more datasets were constructed for cohorts in Europe and Africa. Such synthetic dataset generation then became of high interest by other EuCan projects, in addition to being of use in facilitating appropriate tool development within CINECA. This aided specific use cases, for example in one case for COVID-19 relevant data during the pandemic, and another use case involving sharing of gene expression data. Additional tools were developed to help support this work, including text mining tools and the Data Use Ontology.

While the COVID-19 pandemic has had an impact on many CINECA project participants, particularly some members of WP3 directly involved in the pandemic response, we are pleased that all these resources - including the minimal metadata model, ontologies, text mining tools, and populated synthetic datasets - have been created and are proving to be useful. In addition, a Synthetic Data Best Practices document has been created, and a commentary on the benefits of such resources is being submitted with this Best Practices document for publication. Additional synthetic datasets for other uses are also now being created. The minimal metadata model, the datasets reflecting this model, and the Synthetic Data Best Practices document, are all being made broadly available to aid any project, including those outside of CINECA interested in facilitating cross-jurisdictional data discovery and analysis. We propose that generation of additional synthetic data examples associated with a range of cohorts and use cases may be the key to accelerating data sharing resource development, and help overcome barriers to data sharing for a wide range of biomedical applications.

2. Project objectives

This deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) To define the project's meta data representation needs (Task 3.1).
- b) To define a cross cohort minimal metadata model (Task 3.1).
- c) To deliver best practice for cross cohort meta data representation (Task 3.1).
- d) To populate the minimal metadata model for cohort meta data (Task 3.1).
- e) To develop semantic mapping and data harmonisation strategies in support of analysis WPs (Task 3.2).

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

The goal of CINECA is to enable federated queries and analyses of the varying and wide-ranging datasets from the 10 CINECA cohorts. The role of the minimal metadata model is to be an agreed upon and machine readable standard so that the wide ranging and differing variables from each cohort's dataset can map to standardised and ontologised variables, and thus be harmonised to enable federated querying. The model must be flexible and its variables must be sufficient to cover (1) common CINECA cohort data, (2) any requirements for CINECA use cases, and (3) key cohort metadata commonly collected by renowned data catalogues. To test the usefulness of the model, several synthetic datasets have been created to validate the minimal metadata model and demonstrate ability to harmonise and query data from the CINECA cohorts. Real cohort datasets are not easily usable as there are strict data governance policies around sharing of any sensitive data. Thus, synthetic datasets were created to be used in place of real datasets for purposes such as developing public demonstrators of federated analysis applications. The synthetic datasets are de-identified and obscure sensitive data to allow for public use, but they must also reliably represent the real data types of the original datasets.

3.2 Description of Work

Creation of the Minimal Metadata Model

A first version of the metadata model was built based on a review of Maelstrom research data standards and a manual survey of cohort data dictionaries, which identified and incorporated overlapping core variables across CINECA cohorts. The model was then converted to Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology¹ (GECKO) format and further expanded with additional terms. The minimal metadata model is being made broadly available to aid any project or projects, including those outside of CINECA interested in facilitating cross-jurisdictional data discovery and analysis.

¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/gecko>

See the earlier deliverable for more details regarding how this minimal metadata model was constructed (Appendix 1: Earlier deliverable [D3.1](#)).

As part of these efforts, ontology development and text mining tools were created, to help develop populated datasets:

Semantic Harmonization / GECKO

CINECA's model, the Genomic Cohort Knowledge Ontology (GECKO), was formalised using the Web Ontology Language [OWL](#)², a World Wide Web Consortium standard, and adopts [OBO Foundry](#)³ best practices for ontology development. GECKO leverages and contributes to existing resources for maximal interoperability. It is used in the [International HundredK+ Cohorts Consortium](#)⁴ (IHCC) cohort browser, and has been extended for use by the [Davos Alzheimer's Collaborative consortium](#)⁵. GECKO increases data findability through high-level metadata queries against an interactive, searchable registry that is updated from cohorts regularly. GECKO is [available publicly](#)⁶ (CC-BY).

Data Use Ontology

The Data Use Ontology⁷ (DUO) is a hierarchical vocabulary of machine-readable data use terms which has been developed in collaboration with and approved as a standard by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH). The DUO terms allow the consistent and unambiguous representation of data use conditions in order to discover, gain access to and integrate diverse datasets.

Text mining pipeline

Harmonisation of attributes across different cohorts is not restricted to the cohort data itself; cohorts are also described in scientific publications, and supplementary sections of research papers often contain large amounts of semi-structured data. This supplementary data can contain additional information which both reaffirms and enhances original data and could be very helpful in search and data discovery. Due to its nature and scale, this data is not amenable to manual processing, and instead requires the application of machine learning and Natural Language Processing techniques to extract any useful information.

² <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-syntax/>

³ <http://obofoundry.org/>

⁴ <https://ihccglobal.org/>

⁵ <https://www.davosalzheimerscollaborative.org/>

⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/gecko>

⁷ <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

Fig 1. Text mining pipeline for the extraction of biomedical entities from unstructured text and mapping to standard ontology terms.

The CINECA text mining group has been providing common tools and methods to extract additional metadata from unstructured and semi-structured fields in cohorts' data. WP3 members have written detailed blogs on some of the tools in development - focusing on the CoLaus/PsyCoLaus cohort data, [HES-SO/SIB has developed a pipeline that uses MetaMap and learning-to-rank](https://www.cineca-project.eu/blog-all/assigning-standard-descriptors-to-free-text)⁸ for assigning unambiguous metadata descriptors to free text; [SFU has developed a rule-based text mining tool LexMapr](https://www.cineca-project.eu/blog-all/lexmapr-a-rule-based-text-mining-tool-for-ontology-term-mapping-and-classification)⁹ that cleans up and parses shorter form unstructured text to extract biomedical entities and map these to standard ontology terms; [EMBL-FBI has developed Zooma and Curami pipelines](https://www.cineca-project.eu/blog-all/uncovering-metadata-from-semi-structured-cohort-data)¹⁰ to annotate and curate semi-structured data.

Creation of populated synthetic datasets

Synthetic datasets were constructed by first obtaining real data associated with each minimal metadata field, and then generating synthetic versions of the data, capitalising on the above tools as well as a data harmoniser and a series of Best Practices that were developed through this process. Key was to closely involve the Cohort owners, to ensure suitability of the synthetic data that is realistic, but also not risking identifiability of cohort participants. Some synthetic datasets were more challenging, such as the CHILD Cohort dataset which involved both children and their parents. The CINECA synthetic datasets were eventually generated based on a subset of the phenotypic data from four participating cohorts: UK Biobank, CoLaus, H3Africa, and the CHILD Cohort Study. The values in the datasets are entirely synthesised, having been derived from the parameters of the source dataset. The genotypic variables attributed to the datasets were all derived from fully public data, which was

⁸ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/blog-all/assigning-standard-descriptors-to-free-text>

⁹ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/blog-all/lexmapr-a-rule-based-text-mining-tool-for-ontology-term-mapping-and-classification>

¹⁰ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/blog-all/uncovering-metadata-from-semi-structured-cohort-data>

used to minimise privacy intrusion while maximising the utility of the synthesised datasets by including a range of file and data types.

The initial synthetic datasets are available here, with additional information provided: <https://www.cineca-project.eu/cineca-synthetic-datasets>

Synthetic Datasets - Best Practices:

Initial version, pending publication:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1hqFbm8PdonA2GVs6zKSUMDIKoQ1owrPNW6EF7Rb48Xc/edit#heading=h.r36cfme1z2yt>

Uses of these populated synthetic datasets

Synthetic datasets do not contain any personally identifiable information and cannot be used to make any inference about specific individuals within the cohort or results from analyses of the cohort data. These datasets contain the same types of data and variables, as well as similar distributions and correlations between variables, as the data sets from which they are derived. By examining the synthetic datasets, researchers can determine whether the correct data types exist in the bona fide data set to conduct a study or answer a scientific question. Since they are created based on a minimal metadata model, this ensures data fields containing the same information from different cohorts are harmonised. *Developers* can design and create infrastructure that is capable of housing the data without having access to the actual datasets, and *Researchers* can examine synthetic datasets from multiple cohorts to determine whether the datasets contain the types of data they're interested in studying without having to formally request access to the data itself.

CINECA use case - eQTL analysis

One example of a CINECA use-case that utilised the minimal metadata model and synthetic cohorts is the federated eQTL analysis (WP4). The federated eQTL analysis technical demonstrator¹¹ consists of the following components:

1. Synthetic datasets with harmonised metadata (CINECA WP3)
2. Dataset discovery via GA4GH Beacon (CINECA WP1)
3. Access to data and compute resources via Life Science Login AAI (CINECA WP2)
4. Containerised and portable workflows (see above) (CINECA WP4)

The primary synthetic dataset for the eQTL use cases is the CINECA synthetic cohort EUROPE UK1¹² (CINECA UK1) dataset hosted at the EGA (EGAD00001006673) that contains eQTL data from the GEUVADIS project. To illustrate the flexibility of our eQTL analysis workflows, we have also compiled two additional synthetic datasets leveraging open access single-cell RNA sequencing data from the

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7464116>

¹² <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001006673>

OneK1K project¹³ and microarray gene expression data from the CEDAR project¹⁴. The CINECA minimal metadata model was used to harmonise the metadata between these datasets.

To facilitate data discovery, we worked with our partners from CINECA WP1 and loaded 2 datasets into GA4GH Beacon instances. The CINECA UK1 datasets is currently accessible via the EGA Beacon¹⁵ and the OneK1K dataset is available via the CanDIG Beacon¹⁶. The CINECA UK1 dataset was further made available via the CSC SD Apply¹⁷, which enabled us to demonstrate how the Life Science Login AAI can be used to both apply for access to datasets and then analyse those datasets in a secure cloud environment.

3.3 Next steps

The role of the minimal metadata model is to be an agreed upon and machine readable standard so that the wide ranging and differing variables from each cohort's dataset can map to standardised and ontologised variables, and thus be harmonised to enable federated querying. The model must be flexible and its variables must be sufficient to cover (1) common CINECA cohort data, (2) any requirements for CINECA use cases, and (3) key cohort metadata commonly collected by renowned data catalogues.

We live in an age where research is becoming increasingly collaborative, yet concerns for public privacy can pose a barrier to data sharing. We propose such synthetic datasets can be an important tool to enhance data sharing and allow researchers to conduct studies across jurisdictions. These populated datasets represent just the start of a new approach, involving the combined use of a minimal metadata model, and synthetic data, to help accelerate both tool development and data discovery - including across continents as CINECA has achieved. The synthetic cohort approaches developed by the CINECA project have been adopted by the EOSC4Cancer, B1MG, and the Genome Data Infrastructure (GDI) project as part of the starter kit.

4. Abbreviations

B1MG: Beyond One Million Genomes project

DUO: Data Use Ontology

EGA: European Genome-Phenome Archive

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/record/7619796>

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/6171348>

¹⁵ EGA Beacon: <https://ega-archive.org/beacon-apis/cineca>

¹⁶ CanDIG Beacon: <https://cineca.bento.c3g.calculquebec.ca/api/beacon>

¹⁷ <https://research.csc.fi/en/-/sd-apply>

eQTL: Expression Quantitative Trait Loci

GA4GH: Global Alliance for Genomics and Health

GDI: Genome Data Infrastructure

GECKO: Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology

IHCC: International HundredK+ Cohorts Consortium

OWL: Web Ontology Language

OBO Foundry: Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology Foundry

5. Delivery and schedule

Delivery was delayed due to multiple key researchers in the WP3 work page needing to pivot to support the pandemic response, plus one of the leads sustained a significant head injury in 2021 requiring a 1 year medical leave and then an additional partial recovery period (they have now, as of 2023, recovered and have been catching up with delayed activities).

6. Adjustments made

Given the challenges with sharing real data, the decision was made to create synthetic datasets that were based closely on real data. This turned out to be a non-trivial task, due to the need to ensure synthetic data could not be misinterpreted as real data, ensuring that the data was realistic, yet not leading to any identifiability of the cohort participants real data that the synthetic data was based upon. As a result, a Synthetic Data Best Practices document was produced, to summarise what we learned and help other researchers design appropriate synthetic datasets for cohorts.

7. Appendices

Appendix 1

More details regarding how this minimal metadata model was constructed ([D3.1](#))

Appendix 2

[Synthetic Data Best Practices document](#)

Appendix 3

[Populated Synthetic Cohort Datasets](#)

